

CHARACTERISTICS AND FEATURES OF WHEAT AS A FOOD UNIT IN THE WORLD OF AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Selection Achievements", the Law "On Seed Production in the New Edition" dated 2019 and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated April 21, 2021, it is important to suggest that 683 decisions of scientists in the field of seed production development, regarding the prevention of food security in agriculture impressions remained due to several reasons. In this regard, breeding directions aimed at improving the quality of agricultural products are widely distributed throughout the world. For this purpose, both in the world and in our country, many studies have been published on how to achieve a significant increase in the quality of wheat grain based on the development and implementation of a flexible farming system, taking into account soil and climatic conditions.

Keywords: selection, breed, type, variety, licensor, parthenocloned, hybrids, gluten, polymorphism, vitamins, pigments, enzymes, Australia, South America, Africa, Triticum, Aestivum, wheat grass, Hessian fly, scurvy, Swedish fly, haswa, black rust.

Introduction. It is important to suggest that wheat is the most important food crop. Cereals and grain products make up the main part of the diet of the world's population. In particular, Uzbeks eat a lot of bread, and in this regard, the place of wheat grain in our lives is extremely large. 14% of the world's arable land is occupied by grain fields. Grain products account for 50% of food sales. Accordingly, there is a great demand for wheat products on the world market. For this reason, it is important to conduct research on growing wheat, obtaining a large harvest and improving the quality of wheat flour as soon as possible. The study of the original forms of wheat in order to create high-yielding, high-grain varieties resistant to stressful environmental conditions, the creation of new promising wheat varieties in programs for the division of genetic resources and selection is an urgent task. Wheat is divided into hard and soft. Bread is mainly made from soft wheat. Hard wheat is used in the pasta and confectionery industries. The dough from its flour is dense, slightly elastic or highly elastic, does not form gluten. The problem of improving the quality of wheat grain is relevant in a market economy. High-quality bakery products are obtained from strong wheat grains, which reduces grain consumption.

What is more interesting, wheat grain protein is in the form of protoids and protoins, which play a major role in the preparation of high-quality bread and bakery products. One of the most important indicators of the quality of wheat grain is its protein and gluten content. Gluten is a biochemical compound that determines the elasticity of the dough when making high-quality bread. The chemical composition of wheat grain is very variable. The content of protein, gluten, minerals, vitamins, pigments and enzymes varies depending on the climate, soil and fertilizers applied, agricultural technology and varieties. The requirements of the world standard note that the protein content in wheat grain should not be less than 13.5%. The amount of protein in wheat

grain determines what it is used for. For baking bread, 14-15% protein is required in grain, for pasta - 17-18%.

Definitely, wheat (*Triticum*) is a group of herbaceous plants belonging to the cereal family; the oldest and main grain crop, cultivated today in many countries of the world. There are about 30 wild and cultivated species, differing in the number of chromosomes in somatic cells, belonging to 3 types (diploid, tetraploid, hexaploid). In world agriculture, mainly soft wheat (*Triticum aestivum*, *Triticum vulgare*) and hard wheat (*Triticum durum*) are cultivated. Other species are rarely planted or not planted at all. Transcaucasia is the birthplace of many types of wheat (Ararat, makha, timothy wheat, Urartu, Persian wheat, etc.). Wheat was known in the countries of Old and Central Asia as early as 7-6 thousand years BC. In North America, it has been grown since the 17th century.

Surprisingly, wheat is located on the globe at 66° north latitude (Sweden), and in Russia at the northern latitude (Murmansk region) in experimental areas; in the south it is planted up to the southern borders of Australia, South America and Africa. In the world, the area of wheat cultivation is about 250 million hectares, wheat accounts for about 30% of the grain grown (on average more than 360 million tons).

Botanical description. It is not a secret to anyone, that the root system of wheat is taproot, the main part of which develops in the plowed soil layer, and some roots penetrate to a depth of 180 cm. The stem is straw-shaped, 40-130 cm high. The dormant period and yield of wheat depend on the height of the stem. The leaf consists of a leaf sheath and a ribbon-shaped leaf blade surrounding the stem like a flute. The ear consists of multi-flowered ears with a ball. External pollination in wheat is rare, self-pollination is more common. The fruit is a grain. The grain is naked, oval, ovoid, oblong or spherical, with longitudinal ridges on the ventral side, white or reddish-brown. Depending on the size, it is divided into soft (*Urvokdi*) or hard (shiny, hard) wheat. Weight of 1000 grains is 20-70 g. Ears of soft wheat with and without ears, ears shorter than spikes; grains white or reddish, round in cross-section, mostly starchy inside. Ear of hard wheat is dense, mostly with thorns, ears grow longer and straighter than the cob.

Economic importance. Moreover, grain is nutritious, contains protein (from 10-12% to 20-25% in some varieties, 25-30% in wild species), starch (60-64%), as well as fats (2%), vitamins, enzymes, minerals and more. Grain, bran and other waste are valuable feed, raw material for the feed industry. Straw for feed and bedding, building material; the stem is used to make paper, cardboard, wrapping material, weaving baskets, hats, etc. Blue cellulose is fed to cattle and also ensiled. Various types of flour, semolina, alcohol, starch and other products are made from wheat grain.

Biological properties. Wheat is an annual plant, and perennial varieties of wheat have been created by hybridizing various species and forms (see Wheat hybrids). There are varieties that yield crops in autumn, spring, semi-autumn and autumn and spring. Autumn wheat is biologically different from spring wheat, is resistant to cold and drought, and germinates at a soil temperature of 4-5°C. It is especially demanding of moisture during the flowering period.

Additionally, during the growing season, an effective temperature of 2100° is required for autumn wheat and at least 1300° for spring wheat. Drought reduces productivity. The vegetation period of winter wheat in autumn is 45-50 days, in spring-summer - 75-100 days, spring wheat - 90-100 days. Winter wheat can withstand frosts down to -35° with thick snow cover. Spring

wheatgrass can withstand -8-10° of frost. The yield of autumn wheat is 20-25 (in some cases 70-80) centners/hour on wet lands, the yield of spring wheat is 12-18 centners/hour on dry lands.

Agricultural technology. It is known to everyone that in irrigated regions, winter wheat is recommended to be sown on fertile lands free from corn, cotton, potatoes and other field crops. It grows poorly on acidic and salty soil. Planting method: planted in wide rows (12-15 cm between rows) or narrow rows (7-8 cm between rows). The seeding rate is 70-110 kg/ha on dry lands, 170-200 kg/ha on irrigated areas, planting depth is 4-6 cm; autumn wheat is planted deeper, the planting rate is taken 10-15% more, the seeds are sorted and processed before planting. In irrigated conditions of Uzbekistan, 10-15 tons of manure, 40-80 kg of phosphorus, 40-100 kg of nitrogen, potassium are added to the soil where wheat is sown.

During the growing season, the field is fertilized, irrigated lands are watered 2-3 times during the growing season, in Uzbekistan, ripe wheat fields are immediately harvested by combine harvesters.

Varieties. It is important to suggest that in 1937-96, the wheat variety in Uzbekistan changed 6 times (1937-61; 194464; 196065; 196375; 197080; 198085; 199095). The Milyutin State Selection Center (Gallaorol) was engaged in the creation of wheat seeds and new varieties of wheat. The Research Institute of Corn and Leguminous Crops (Gallaorol branch of Andijan city) carried out important work on the current wetlands. On irrigated fields - wheat Kyltiksiz B. (Bezostaya 1), Unumli, Sete Serros, Sanggor 4, Intensive, Yonbosh, Red wheat (variety Kad. Jaidari) - on dry lands. Kizil Shalola (Krasnovodopadskaya 210), Surkhok 5688, Tezpushar and other varieties were planted. Since 1995, the varieties Skifyanka and Yuna, brought from the Krasnodar Territory of Russia, Ukraine, are capable of yielding 50-70 c/ha on irrigated fields. Wheat pests: grain aphid, Hessian fly, whitefly, Swedish fly, midge, etc. Diseases: black moth, black rust, powdery mildew and others.

Originator of the variety: Selection variety of the Research Institute of Grain and Leguminous Plants on Irrigated Lands.

Authors of the variety: Siddikov R.I., Teshaboyev S.E.

Biological autumn. Belongs to the Lutessens type. The head is pyramidal in shape, medium in length, white. The grain is large, red, ovoid. The average weight of 1000 grains is from 40.4 to 58.0 g.

Average plant height: from 80 cm to 105 cm.

Evaluation of resistance to lodging and shattering - 5.0. Winter hardiness is 5.0 points. The average yield on irrigated state variety testing plots is from 38.0 to 72.9 c/ha. The vegetation period is 185-225 days. According to the Republican Grain Inspection Laboratory, the bread coating score of the variety is 2.5 points. The gluten content is 25%.

Recommended for planting in all regions of our country.

Besides that, Nurafshon is an autumn soft wheat developed by the Research Institute of Plant Growing. Ripens in 212-216 days, medium height (89.0-95.0 cm). Weight of 1000 seeds is 42.8-43.8 g, resistant to yellow and brown rust, heat and dormancy. The head is cylindrical, of medium density. Productivity is 69.3-72.5 c/ha.

By summerising it should be suggested that the Resistant variety was developed by the Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources, the general description of which is medium-sized variety, ripens in 212-214 days, low-growing (79.8-83.7 cm), which is resistant to yellow and brown rust, heat and lodging, moderately resistant to salt, weight of 1000 pcs. Is 40.3-40.9 g.

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